

FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF FRIENDSHIP AND COOPERATION IN INTERETHNIC RELATIONS IS THE BASIS OF HIGH PROGRESS

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Abstract: This article highlights that the development of a culture of tolerance and humanism in our country is defined as one of the most important priorities of state policy, and the further development of friendship and harmony in interethnic relations is the basis of high progress.

Keywords: friendship, solidarity, tolerance, humanism, patriotism, interethnic harmony, interethnic relations.

From the first years of independence, strengthening interethnic and interfaith harmony, ensuring interethnic harmony, developing a culture of tolerance and humanism, educating the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism, respect for national and universal values have been identified in our country as one of the most important priorities of state policy.

Today, more than 7.0 billion people live on Earth. Of the more than 1,600 ethnic groups in the world, only about 200 have national statehood.

Uzbekistan is a multinational (multiethnic) state. According to available data, more than a hundred years ago, about 70 nationalities lived on the territory of the current republic. After 30 years, this number reached 91, in 1959-113, in 1979-123 seriously [1].

In the structure of the population of the republic in 1991, the share of Uzbeks in the total population was 72.8%, Karakalpaks – 2.1%, Russians – 7.7%, Tajiks – 4.8%, Kazakhs - 4.1%, Tatars – 2%, Ukrainians - 0.7%. Therefore, after the declaration of independence in 1991, the unification and consolidation of

representatives of all nationalities and nationalities living in Uzbekistan around our national ideology became an important issue [2].

As the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, the focus of our attention will be the further development of mutual friendship and harmony reigning in our society, ensuring equal rights for all citizens, regardless of their nationality, religion and religion. The dissemination of extremist and radical ideas that cause enmity between them is strictly prohibited in Uzbekistan [3].

Article 4 of our Constitution states: "The state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan is Uzbek. The Republic of Uzbekistan ensures respect for the languages, traditions and customs of all nationalities and nationalities living on its territory, creates conditions for their development" [4]. The fact that our country has created ample opportunities for teaching representatives of all nationalities and nationalities in their native language, this is practiced in higher educational institutions and schools, newspapers and magazines are published in many languages, TV and radio broadcasts are conducted, etc., is evidenced by fruitful work in this direction.

As can be seen, Uzbekistan has gained a unique experience in the proper establishment of interethnic relations. At the same time, the principle was observed not only to foster national consciousness, a sense of national pride and pride, to preserve the language, culture, traditions of peoples, but also to achieve the common unity of all nations in the country.

This policy was built on the initiative of the First President of our country Islam Karimov:

- ✓ recognition of multi-nationality as a factor with creative power;
- ✓ ensuring equality of citizens regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, beliefs, personality, social origin and status;
- ✓ guarantee equal participation of citizens in the political and public life of the country, regardless of their nationality;
- ✓ ensuring respect for the national language, traditions and customs and creating favorable conditions for their development;

- ✓ ensuring the development of society based on the diversity of public life, political institutions, ideologies and opinions;
- ✓ prevention of activities that promote national, racial, religious hostility and conflicts directed against the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens;
- ✓ it is consistently implemented based on principles such as the recognition of the priority of international rules regarding the protection of the rights and freedoms of nations and nationalities [5].

We should not forget that where the importance of the idea of interethnic harmony is not realized, various conflicts and problems arise in the life of society that threaten peace and stability. This is evidenced by the national conflicts taking place today in some regions of the world.

The experience of our republic in strengthening interethnic harmony is studied with interest in many countries of the world. The foreign press, well-known politicians and leaders highly appreciate the national policy of Uzbekistan. While national-ethnic relations are becoming more complicated in some countries of the world, national-ethnic relations are becoming more complicated in some States, discrimination of minority representatives is also observed in some states, Uzbekistan, living in unity, cooperation, as children of one family, is undoubtedly an example for others today. Walking around our capital, we see that along with sculptures of Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, monuments of Ganjavi, Rustaveli, Pushkin, Shevchenko decorate our streets and squares. All this is a vivid expression of interreligious tolerance and interethnic harmony [6].

It should be noted that ensuring unity, friendly relations between more than 130 nationalities and peoples living in our native land, and their huge contribution to the good of our Motherland instill in each of us a sense of confidence in the future. Such work serves to form in the minds of the younger generation a respectful attitude to the language, religion and traditions of representatives of other nationalities.

The legislation of some states establishes that in order to become the head of state, it is necessary to be born in this country or have an ethnicity. From this it can

be seen that in relation to interethnic relations, the Constitution of Uzbekistan is more democratic than the Constitutions of some developed democratic states.

In some countries of the world, even today, one can observe conflicts and wars taking place on national grounds (for example, the conflict between Azerbaijan and Armenia, Arab and Kurdish clashes in Iraq, etc.). This will be possible if countries use the legislation and practice of Uzbekistan to ensure interethnic harmony.

In short, the greatest wealth of our society is peace and harmony. Only in a country where the principles of tolerance and humanism prevail, a person can live freely, achieve any dream. At the same time, as the head of our state noted, our greatest wealth is, first of all, the purity of the sky of our Motherland, the atmosphere of interethnic harmony, friendship and solidarity reigning in our society. It is the sacred duty of all of us to value peace and protect our country, in which representatives of different nationalities and nationalities live in peace and harmony as children of the same family.

REFERENCES:

1. Bekmurodov A. Bu muqaddas Vatanda azizdir inson. -T.: "Ma'naviyat", 2010. – B.52.
2. Isroilov B. Bag'ri butunlik belgisi. // "Ma'naviy hayot" tarixiy-falsafiy, ma'naviy-ma'rifiy, ilmiy-ommabop jurnal. №2, 2018 yil.
3. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev. Milliy taraqqiyot yo'limizni qat'iyat bilan davom ettirib, yangi bosqichga ko'taramiz. 1-tom., 138-bet –Toshkent-"O'zbekiston" 2019.
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Konstitutsiyasi. -T.: "O'zbekiston", 2020. -B.4-5.
5. 2017 - 2021-yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshta ustuvor yo'nalishi bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasini "Xalq bilan muloqot va inson manfaatlarini yili"da amalga oshirishga oid Davlat dasturini o'rganish bo'yicha ilmiy-uslubiy risola. -T.: "Ma'naviyat", 2017. -B.362.
6. Quronboyev Q.Q., Madjidov I.U., Xodiyev B.Yu., Umurzoqov O'.P., Bekmurodov A.Sh. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning

Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti Bosh Assambleyasining 72-sessiyasidagi nutqini o'rganish bo'yicha ilmiy-ommabop risola. –T.: “Ma’naviyat”, 2017. –B.147.

7. Sobirovich T. B. A study of national and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 5. – S. 417-421.

8. Sobirovich T. B. Interethnic Harmony And Religious Tolerance-An Integral Part of The Ancient Traditions Of The Uzbeks.

9. Turdiev B. S. EVOLUTION OF IDEAS AND VIEWS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEMOCRATIC SOCIETY AND SPIRITUAL RENEWALS //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2020. – T. 2. – №. 10. – S. 209-217.

10. Sobirovich T. B., Ikrom o'g'li I. M. ISSUE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY IN THE VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS // " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – S. 111-114.

11. Sobirovich T. B. National and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 1. – S. 334-338.

12. Sobirovich T. B. National and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 1. – C. 334-338.

13. Sobirovich T. B. The implementation of human indicator reforms in Uzbekistan //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 9. – C. 197-202.

14. Sobirovich T. B. Issues of gender equality in uzbekistan: Strategy of reforms //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 9. – C. 203-207.

15. Sobirovich T. B. National Principles of Democracy in Uzbekistan //Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS). – 2021. – T. 5. – №. 3. – C. 131-135.

16. Sobirovich T. B. Philosophical Dialectics of National and Universal Cultural Development //Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science & Research (IIJSR). – 2021.

17. Turdiyev B. S. The role of national harmony in the strategy of spiritual renewal //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 229-233.

18. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of Renewal of National Spirituality of Uzbekistan //International Journal on Integrated Education. – 2020. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 122-126.

19. Sobirovich T. B., Murodogli I. S. The strategy for the implementation of the modern governance system in Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 5. – С. 741-748.

20. Sobirovich T. B. Strategy of spiritual renewal in Uzbekistan //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – Т. 24. – №. 06.

21. Sobirovich T. B. The criterion of human indicators in development and renewals in Uzbekistan //EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR). – 2020. – Т. 6. – №. 8. – С. 509-511.

22. Sobirovich T. B. O‘‘zbekiston demokratik jamiyat taraqqiyoti rivojida ma‘‘naviy yangilanishlar strategiyasining roli //Imom Buxoriy saboqlari. – 2020. – №. 2. – С. 118-121.

23. Turdiev B. S., Yuldashev B. T. THE ISSUE OF AVOIDING CRIMES AMONG YOUNGSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN //Экономика и социум. – 2019. – №. 1-1. – С. 119-122.

24. Turdiyev B. S. SPIRITUAL RENEWAL AND INTERETHNIC RELATIONS IN THE STRATEGY OF ACTIONS //Теория и практика современной науки. – 2018. – №. 3. – С. 85-89.

25. Sobirovich T. B. The development of democratic society and spiritual renewal in the views of Eastern and Western thinkers //INTERNATIONAL

